
Deliverable D4.3

Report on dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement – v2

Editor(s):	J. Favaro, J. Arteza, Z. Smith
Responsible Partner:	Trust-IT
Status-Version:	Final - v1.0
Date:	15/07/2023
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

Project Number:	GA 957044
Project Title:	SWForum.eu

Title of Deliverable:	Plan for dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement
Due Date of Delivery to the EC	30.06.2023

Workpackage responsible for the Deliverable:	WP4 - Communication, Dissemination and MTRL
Editor(s):	Trust-IT
Contributor(s):	POLIMI, UOXF, TECNALIA, Conceptivity
Reviewer(s):	Juncal Alonso (TECNALIA)
Approved by:	All Partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	WP1-4

Abstract:	This document provides information on how the project has targeted the main target stakeholders through various channels, such as the SWForum.eu website, social media, events, and webinars, etc. The document also reports on quantitative and qualitative measures demonstrating the impact of the project.
Keyword List:	Software, cybersecurity, infrastructure, open-source, branding, outreach, webinar, workshop,
Licensing information:	This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported (CC BY-SA 3.0) http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/
Disclaimer	This document reflects only the author's views and neither Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

Document Description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	31.05.2023	Table of contents	J. Arteza
v0.2	05.06.2023	Initial update	J. Favaro, J. Arteza, Z. Smith
v0.3	26.06.2023	Section 1-4	J. Favaro, J. Arteza
v0.4	07.07.2023	Final version after modifications as a result of the internal consortium quality review	J. Favaro, J. Arteza
v0.5	07.07.2023	Internal review	TECNALIA
v1.0	07.07.2022	Ready for submission	Juncal Alonso (TECNALIA)

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	5
List of Tables	6
Terms and abbreviations	6
Executive Summary	8
1 Introduction and scope of the document	9
1.1 Goals and related deliverables	9
2 Strategy for Impact Assessment of Communication and Dissemination Activities	11
2.1 Strategy for Stakeholder Engagement	11
2.2 Strategy for communication and dissemination	11
3 Stakeholder engagement and impacts	12
3.1 R&I Projects	12
3.1.1 Project Radar and Hub	12
3.1.1.1 Community	14
3.1.1.2 Engagement campaigns	15
3.1.2 Workshops	16
3.1.2.1 Community	18
3.1.2.2 Engagement	20
3.1.3 Webinars	21
3.1.3.1 Community	24
3.1.3.2 Engagement	24
3.2 Software development organisations and industry players	25
3.2.1 Open Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability	25
3.2.1.1 Engagement	27
3.2.2 Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT	28
3.2.2.1 Engagement	28
3.3 European Software and Open-source Experts	29
3.3.1 Open Call for Fellowship Applications	29
3.3.1.1 Engagement	30
3.3.1 Online SW Forum	30
3.3.1.1 Engagement	33
4 Communication and Dissemination Impacts	35
4.1 Website	35
4.1.1 Website Performance	36
4.2 Social media	38

4.2.1	Twitter	38
4.2.2	LinkedIn	39
4.3	Graphically-designed materials	41
4.4	Videos	42
4.5	Newsletters	43
4.6	Events and Webinars	44
5	Conclusions	46
6	References	47
ANNEX I – List of Events		49
ANNEX II – List of Project Synergies		50

List of Figures

<i>FIGURE 1: SWFORUM.EU IN NUMBERS (M1-M33)</i>	9
<i>FIGURE 2: SWFORUM.EU PROJECT HUB AND FEATURED PROJECT SPOTLIGHT – TWITTER PROMOTIONS</i>	12
<i>FIGURE 3: SWFORUM.EU PROJECT HUB</i>	13
<i>FIGURE 4: SWFORUM.EU PROJECT HUB AND FEATURED PROJECT SPOTLIGHT – TWITTER PROMOTIONS</i>	14
<i>FIGURE 5: PROJECTS FEATURED IN THE PROJECT SPOTLIGHT</i>	14
<i>FIGURE 6: PROJECTS IN THE SWFORUM.EU PROJECT HUB ACCORDING TO FUNDING SCHEME AND FUNDING PROGRAMME</i>	15
<i>FIGURE 7: SWFORUM.EU WORKSHOPS, ORGANISED AND CO-LOCATED</i>	16
<i>FIGURE 8: BRANDING MATERIALS CREATED AND CAPTURED DURING THE WEGREEN WORKSHOP, 15 SEP 2022, SLOVENIA/HYBRID</i>	17
<i>FIGURE 9: BRANDING MATERIALS CREATED DURING THE EC WORKSHOP, 2 DEC 2022, BRUSSELS</i>	17
<i>FIGURE 10: EVENT BRANDED BANNER DURING THE FIRST FAST CONTINUUM 2023, 16 APR 2023, PORTUGAL</i>	17
<i>FIGURE 11: EVENT BRANDED MATERIALS AND LIVE SOCIAL MEDIA POST DURING THE WAY FORWARD: WORKSHOP ON FUTURE CHALLENGES IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, 27 JUNE, ITALY</i>	18
<i>FIGURE 12: SWFORUM.EU WORKSHOPS: SPEAKERS AND ATTENDEES</i>	20
<i>FIGURE 13: SWFORUM.EU WEBINARS – MTRL</i>	21
<i>FIGURE 14: SWFORUM.EU WEBINARS – THEMATIC TOPICS</i>	22
<i>FIGURE 15: SWFORUM.EU WEBINARS – TWITTER LIVE COVERAGE</i>	23
<i>FIGURE 16: GLOBAL IMPACT OF SWFORUM.EU WEBINARS</i>	24
<i>FIGURE 17: OPEN SOURCE WORKSHOP – PHOTO GALLERY</i>	26
<i>FIGURE 18: OPEN SOURCE WORKSHOP – AGENDA</i>	26
<i>FIGURE 19: OPEN SOURCE WORKSHOP – REPORTS</i>	27
<i>FIGURE 20: OPEN CALL FOR FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME – SOCIAL MEDIA PROMOTION AND KEY RESULT</i>	29
<i>FIGURE 21: SWFORUM.EU FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME - WEBPAGE</i>	30
<i>FIGURE 22: ONLINE SWFORUM DISCUSSION – WEBPAGE</i>	31
<i>FIGURE 23: ONLINE SW-FORUM DISCUSSION – WEBSITE PROMOTIONS</i>	32
<i>FIGURE 24: ONLINE SW-FORUM DISCUSSION – SOCIAL MEDIA PROMOTIONS</i>	33
<i>FIGURE 25: SWFORUM.EU WEBSITE STRUCTURE - NEW</i>	36
<i>FIGURE 26: SWFORUM.EU WEBSITE STATISTICS – USAGE DATA</i>	37
<i>FIGURE 27: SWFORUM.EU WEBSITE STATISTICS – PAGEVIEWS</i>	37
<i>FIGURE 28: SWFORUM.EU WEBSITE TRAFFIC BY COUNTRY</i>	38
<i>FIGURE 29: SWFORUM.EU TWITTER PERFORMANCE</i>	39

FIGURE 30: SWFORUM.EU DASHBOARD: TWITTER ENGAGEMENT..... 39
 FIGURE 31: SWFORUM.EU LINKEDIN PERFORMANCE, FROM 4 JULY 2022 – 3 JULY 2023 40
 FIGURE 32: SWFORUM.EU DASHBOARD: TWITTER ENGAGEMENT..... 40
 FIGURE 33: SWFORUM.EU LINKEDIN FOLLOWERS’ DEMOGRAPHICS BY INDUSTRY AND JOB FUNCTION 41
 FIGURE 34: EXAMPLES OF GRAPHIC BANNERS 41
 FIGURE 35: EXAMPLES OF GRAPHIC BANNERS 42
 FIGURE 36: SWFORUM.EU VIDEO – WEBPAGE 43
 FIGURE 37: SAMPLE OF SHORT GIF VIDEO FOR SOCIAL MEDIA PROMOTION..... 43
 FIGURE 38: SWFORUM.EU NEWSLETTER ISSUES..... 44

List of Tables

TABLE 1: RELATED DELIVERABLES..... 9
 TABLE 2: HUB AND RADAR FOR R&I PROJECTS: ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGNS, ACTIVITIES AND IMPACTS..... 15
 TABLE 3: SWFORUM.EU WORKSHOPS ATTENDEES (ORGANISED AND CO-LOCATED EVENTS) - IMPACTS AND OUTREACH RESULTS 19
 TABLE 4: SWFORUM.EU WORKSHOPS: ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGNS, ACTIVITIES AND IMPACTS 20
 TABLE 5: LIST OF SWFORUM.EU WEBINARS – IMPACTS AND OUTREACH RESULTS 23
 TABLE 6: SWFORUM.EU WORKSHOPS: ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGNS, ACTIVITIES AND IMPACTS 24
 TABLE 7: OPEN SOURCE WORKSHOPS FOR COMPUTING & SUSTAINABILITY – ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGNS, ACTIVITIES AND IMPACTS 27
 TABLE 8: CONCERTATION AND CONSULTATION ON COMPUTING CONTINUUM: FROM CLOUD TO EDGE TO IOT – ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGNS, ACTIVITIES AND IMPACTS..... 28
 TABLE 9: OPEN CALL FOR FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME – ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGNS, ACTIVITIES AND IMPACTS. 30
 TABLE 10: ONLINE SWFORUM – PUBLISHED BLOGS..... 31
 TABLE 11: OPEN CALL FOR FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME – ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGNS, ACTIVITIES AND IMPACTS 34
 TABLE 12: SWFORUM.EU WEBSITE PERFORMANCE – STATISTICS UPDATE 37
 TABLE 13: SWFORUM.EU TWITTER PERFORMANCE UPDATE 39
 TABLE 14: SWFORUM.EU LINKEDIN PERFORMANCE..... 40
 TABLE 15: NEWSLETTER PERFORMANCE 44
 TABLE 16: EVENTS (M19-M33) – ORGANISED AND PARTICIPATED EVENTS 49
 TABLE 17: EC PROJECT SYNERGIES (M1-M33) 50

Terms and abbreviations

CMM	Capability Maturity Model
CMS	Content Management System
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CPT	CONCEPTIVITY SARL
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key exploitable results
MTRL	Market Technology Readiness Level
POLIMI	POLITECNICO DI MILANO
R&I	Research and Innovation
SW	Software

SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
TECNALIA	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION
TRUST-IT	TRUST-IT SRL
UOXF	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD
UX	User experience
WP	Work Package

DRAFT

Executive Summary

This document is a direct outcome of WP4 (Communication, Dissemination, and MTRL), which played a vital role in the project by effectively raising awareness of project results, disseminating key outputs, and engaging key stakeholders.

Its purpose is two-fold:

Firstly, it presents an overview of the implementation plan that the project has executed to establish a European stakeholder community in the software and open-source sectors.

Secondly, it provides concrete evidence of the impact generated by the various activities carried out while establishing connections to the principal outcomes produced by SWForum.eu.

Consequently, the document furnishes detailed information on how the project has reached and engaged the primary target stakeholders through diverse channels such as the SWForum.eu website, social media platforms, events, webinars, and more. Furthermore, it presents both quantitative and qualitative measures, showcasing the tangible impact of the project resulting from the dissemination and communication activities and the SWForum.eu team's efforts to engage stakeholders from M19 (April 2022) to June 2023 (M33).

1 Introduction and scope of the document

This document represents the final iteration of the communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement plan for the SWForum.eu project, falling under the purview of Work Package 4 (WP4) titled "Communication, Dissemination, and MTRL." Serving as an update to the D4.2 Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Engagement report [1] submitted in M18, it offers a comprehensive overview of the plan's implementation progress up until M33.

By engaging with key stakeholders, the document provides evidence of the tangible impact generated by the project. It demonstrates how the plan reached and involved these stakeholders, thereby showcasing the project's ability to create meaningful connections and foster valuable engagement. Figure 1 shows in a nutshell the main achievements of SWForum.eu to date (M1-M33).

Figure 1: SWForum.eu in Numbers (M1-M33)

1.1 Goals and related deliverables

WP4, titled *Communication, Dissemination, and MTRL*, plays a crucial role in the SWForum.eu project by communicating project objectives and disseminating results to the intended stakeholders. As a result, all deliverables produced are highly pertinent to the activities conducted under WP4, related to the support and coordination measures – related work packages (WP2 - EU cross-fertilisation and mapping, and WP3 – Sustainable SWForum.eu and R&I Roadmaps), serving as valuable sources of content for the project's website and social media platforms, among other communication channels. In particular, the following deliverables (Table1), which were also submitted in M33, are closely related to this deliverable.

Table 1: Related deliverables

Deliverable	Title	WP	Lead
D2.3	Cross-fertilization workshop report – v3	2	POLIMI
D2.7	Project Radar Landscape Analysis	2	UOXF
D3.2	Landscape Report – v2	3	CPT
D3.5	Software Forum Research Roadmap - v3	3	TECNALIA
D3.8	Fellowship programme, governance structure and business model for SWForum.eu - v3	3	POLIMI
D4.5	MTRL methodology and assessments - v2	4	UOXF

DRAFT

2 Strategy for Impact Assessment of Communication and Dissemination Activities

As outlined in D4.2, the SWForum.eu team has implemented communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement strategies in order to successfully engage with the Stakeholder Groups described in Section 3. The key strategies, already presented in D4.1 [2] and D4.2 [1], are recapped in the following.

2.1 Strategy for Stakeholder Engagement

- ▣ Profiling and tracking the community's development and growth, including participants from third-party events and SWForum.eu webinars, to understand the community's progress.
- ▣ Selecting appropriate venues for stakeholder engagement, such as third-party events, SWForum.eu webinar series, and workshops, to foster meaningful interactions.
- ▣ Promoting events and maintaining networking efforts through various digital channels, collaborations with like-minded organisations, research projects, and associations to reach a wider audience and create synergies.
- ▣ Reporting on event outcomes, takeaways, and impacts by gathering stakeholder information, assessing geographical distribution, and incorporating insights from Q&A sessions and polls to provide comprehensive feedback.
- ▣ Maintaining regular social media activity and monitoring platforms like LinkedIn and Twitter, to increase project visibility, disseminate project outputs, and highlight upcoming events.
- ▣ Assessing the overall impact of engagement, including monitoring online forum blogs and evaluating the effectiveness of communication efforts.
- ▣ Engaging with relevant projects in software technology, digital infrastructure, and cybersecurity domains to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing.

2.2 Strategy for communication and dissemination

- ▣ Continuing the communication strategy outlined in [1], which monitors impacts based on defined KPIs.
- ▣ Increasing engagement through webinars, YouTube event playlists, and newsletters ensures the community stays updated on new developments and opportunities while leveraging established synergies.
- ▣ Conducting large-scale promotional campaigns for webinars, targeting the EU software stakeholder network and influential synergies in the software ecosystem.
- ▣ Regularly updating the SWForum.eu website and measuring impact through a dedicated dashboard.
- ▣ Running weekly Twitter and LinkedIn campaigns, including SMART-based campaigns for events, to recruit attendees, disseminate key takeaways, and provide live coverage.
- ▣ Publishing joint recommendation reports to showcase the achievements of the SWForum.eu webinar series in thematic topics.
- ▣ Measuring the overall impacts of the communications strategy to assess its effectiveness.

3 Stakeholder engagement and impacts

In response to the M18 review and reviewer recommendations, SWForum.eu enhanced its targeting of stakeholder groups, with a particular emphasis on three key groups: R&I projects, software development organisations and industry players, and European software and open-source experts and people benefiting from the project results.

These stakeholders are directly associated with specific project outputs and have been consistently engaged through various channels. The following sections provide detailed information on the channels used to foster synergies and collaboration with these stakeholders. In Figure 2, some of the most engaged community members which the team leveraged to reach a wider array of stakeholders.

Figure 2: SWForum.eu Project Hub and featured Project Spotlight – Twitter Promotions

3.1 R&I Projects

From the project's inception, SWForum.eu has maintained ongoing collaboration with R&I projects and teams, involving them in various activities such as events, webinars, promotional campaigns, and communication and dissemination support. These activities are closely tied to the advancement and evolution of key outputs within SWForum.eu, which include the Project Radar and Hub, workshops, and webinars. In the subsequent sections, we provide a comprehensive breakdown of each output, highlighting the principal activities undertaken and the resulting impact achieved.

3.1.1 Project Radar and Hub

The Project Radar and Project Hub are closely coupled, and are therefore described together in this section.

In 2022, SWForum.eu launched its second Project Radar version, which visualizes information about projects in two different ways. In its two main views—overall landscape radar and

segmental view—each project is visualized as a "blip—a circle with a number in it and a coloured outline. Further details are provided in [3]. Unlike the previous version, the live radar:

- Adapted the Cyberwatching radar to develop the new SWForum.eu radar, removed the Drop ring from Cyberwatching, and added an Open-Source ring instead to display open-source projects.
- Kept 3 segments instead of 6 in the original Cyberwatching. Each segment has three sub-segments that allow for secondary project classification and align the projects in the segment accordingly.
- New projects are shown in a triangular blip and are changed to a circle 6 months after they are added to the radar to distinguish them from older projects.
- All these tools were developed using open-source tools such as PugJS, NodeJS, and MongoDB for database management.

The radar also provides unique data gathered directly from the projects themselves to provide an up-to-date status:

- MTRL score self-assessments performed by 24 ongoing projects.
- Information on current activities and direct contact through mini-sites by 65 projects **hosted by the SWForum.eu Project Hub.**

The Radar is specifically designed to cater to policymakers and the research community searching for a strategic overview of the software technology R&D landscape in Europe today. Inspired by the original Technology Radar from Thoughtworks, it is tailored specifically for the software domain. It incorporates a customized taxonomy to offer a comprehensive visual presentation of our database of projects across various key dimensions. For further information on the value proposition of the Radar, please refer to [3].

The Project Hub (Figure 3) launched the **Project Spotlight** initiative (Figure 5) in its second term, showcasing selected projects within the hub. These initiatives were designed to foster collaboration and knowledge-sharing among projects in the software ecosystem. We carefully curated a diverse collection of projects, considering their relevance and potential impact. It is important to note that many projects in the software ecosystem are relatively young and may not have had sufficient time to demonstrate tangible results. This motivated us to highlight these projects through our webinar series (Section 3.1.3).

Figure 3: SWForum.eu Project Hub

The Project Hub has provided a platform for these projects to share their ongoing work, challenges, and aspirations with the wider community.

Figure 4: SWForum.eu Project Hub and featured Project Spotlight – Twitter Promotions

This creates valuable opportunities for insight, learning, and collaboration among project teams (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Projects featured in the Project Spotlight

3.1.1.1 Community

Figure 6 provides an overview of the R&I projects featured in the SWForum.eu Project Hub. Both the **Radar and Hub operate as parallel streams**, serving as key channels for engaging with projects. Notably, 86% of the projects included in the Hub have also undergone analysis in the Radar. Furthermore, 61.54% of ongoing projects have self-assessed and validated their data. This demonstrates the active participation and engagement of projects within the SWForum.eu ecosystem, showcasing their commitment to sharing valuable information and fostering collaboration.

Figure 6: Projects in the SWForum.eu Project Hub according to Funding scheme and Funding Programme

3.1.1.2 Engagement campaigns

A series of campaigns have been carried out. The impact of these is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Hub and Radar for R&I projects: Engagement campaigns, activities and impacts

Engagement Campaign	Activities	Impact
Recruitment campaign for the Project Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personalised email invitation One-on-one follow-up interaction with the 64 projects in the Project Hub. 	Since M18, 53% of the contacted projects have created and/or updated their mini page
Project Spotlight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media post creation Promotional banner featuring on SWForum.eu website and social media channels Engaged in a webinar 	Featured 14 projects in the Project Spotlight initiative. See the complete list [4]
Live Radar campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tagging campaign with MTRL assessment done by UOXF partner Personalised email invitation One-on-one follow-up interaction for validation purposes 	<p>A dedicated campaign for validating the projects data was carried out targeting only ongoing projects (37). As a result:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 64.9% were MTRL assessed 24 projects have validated MTRL scores, 10 projects were validated twice <p>Achieved 13.3K total impressions for Twitter promotions</p>

3.1.2 Workshops

Throughout its 33-month existence, SWForum.eu has successfully hosted seven workshops (Figure 7) , playing a crucial role in fostering collaboration among active software technology projects. These workshops have served as pivotal events, igniting future project activities and driving innovation in the field.

Figure 7: SWForum.eu Workshops, organised and co-located

In response to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the format of the first three workshops underwent a transformation from an original design of interactive one-day physical gatherings into an online format. Embracing the need for adaptation, we successfully organised the event in a virtual format, which not only allowed us to overcome physical limitations but also enabled us to extend our reach and attract a more diverse and extensive audience. This expansion has surpassed the boundaries of the EC-funded project community, facilitating engagement with a wider range of participants.

The main objective was to organise and deliver workshops involving stakeholders from both academia, industry and the public sector, representing different domains and application sectors. Here are some glimpses and materials created for each event.

Figure 8: Branding materials created and captured during the WEGREEN workshop, 15 Sep 2022, Slovenia/Hybrid

Figure 9: Branding materials created during the EC Workshop, 2 Dec 2022, Brussels

Figure 10: Event branded banner during the First Fast Continuum 2023, 16 Apr 2023, Portugal

Figure 11: Event branded materials and live social media post during the Way Forward: Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering, 27 June, Italy

The team implemented a pay-per-click campaign as a strategic approach to enhance the event's promotion and reach. The rationale behind the pay-per-click campaign was to drive increased attendance, engagement, and participation by leveraging targeted online advertising channels.

More detailed information on these workshops can be found in [5].

3.1.2.1 Community

Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, the workshops have successfully achieved their main objective of gathering almost 500 attendees and involved stakeholders from academia, industry, and the public sector. These workshops have been instrumental in reaching a larger

and more diverse audience, fostering collaboration, and facilitating meaningful discussions on important topics within the project domain. By bringing together stakeholders from different domains and application sectors, the workshops have created a platform for cross-pollination of ideas, knowledge exchange, and collaboration. The workshops (both virtual and live) have provided a valuable opportunity for participants to engage in insightful discussions and explore innovative solutions to address the challenges within their respective fields. Here are just a few examples taken from the set of topics discussed during the workshops, which demonstrate the cross-cutting variety that arose over the arc of the project duration:

- ❑ Green software
- ❑ Measuring the sustainability of software
- ❑ Secure software development
- ❑ Software Engineering for Artificial Intelligence / Artificial Intelligence for Software Engineering
- ❑ European sovereignty in software engineering.

Table 3 provides a complete list of the workshops together with attendance figures and outreach results, and Figure 12 provides an overview of speaker / attendee participation levels.

Table 3: SWForum.eu Workshops Attendees (organised and co-located events) - Impacts and Outreach results

Workshop	Date, Category	No° of Attendees	Page views
First SWForum Workshop on Trustworthy Software and Open Source [6]	23-25 March 2021, Online	86	254
Second SWForum.eu Workshop: Research Challenges, Collaboration, and Coordination in European Software Engineering Projects [7]	29 June - 1 July 2021, Online	29	374
First SWForum.eu Sustainability Workshop [8]	19 January 2022, Online	36	32
WEGreen Workshop (in collaboration with HUB4CLOUD) [9]	15 September 2022, Hybrid, Slovenia	39	804
Open Source Workshop for Computing and Sustainability (in collaboration with the European Commission) [10]	2 December 2022, Brussels, Belgium	200	4944
The First Fast Continuum Workshop (Joint workshop with PIACERE and AI-SPRINT in conjunction with ICPE 2023) [11]	16 April 2023, Coimbra, Portugal	40	207
SWForum.eu The Way Forward: Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering [12]	27 June 2023, Milan, Italy	43	869

Figure 12: SWForum.eu Workshops: Speakers and Attendees

3.1.2.2 Engagement

A series of campaigns have been carried out. The impact of these is summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: SWForum.eu Workshops: Engagement campaigns, activities and impacts

Engagement Campaign	Activities	Impact
Agenda definition and logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Personalised email invitation ☐ One-on-one calls to plan sessions and participation ☐ Shaping of different sessions, spanning presentations, panels and roundtables ☐ Rehearsal calls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Nearly 20 EC-projects over 100 software experts from the European Commission, industries, and academies were engaged to contribute to the agenda shaping and participate as speakers or panellists in the SWForum.eu-organised workshops. ☐ 85 projects were engaged by participating in the SWForum.eu-organised and co-located workshops.
Promotional campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Event branding identity ☐ Event communication packages ☐ Social media post creation ☐ Personalised email invitation ☐ Dedicated newsletters ☐ Social media coverages for Pre, Post and during event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Increase of 55.41% in terms of unique visits to the Project Hub ☐ Gained 7.5K event page views ☐ Achieved 39.5K total impressions for Twitter promotions ☐ Continuous social media engagement with growth in followers

The success of the virtual workshops highlights the resilience and adaptability of the project in adapting to the circumstances and leveraging technology to connect with and engage with a wide range of stakeholders. These workshops have not only achieved their intended objective but have also created a lasting impact by fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing among diverse stakeholders.

3.1.3 Webinars

SWForum.eu has successfully organized a total of six webinars, consisting of three MTRL-focused webinars and three thematic webinars. These webinars served as a highly effective platform to keep users updated on the latest advancements in the software community landscape. Through relatable examples, key insights, and lessons learned, the provided valuable guidance on the Market and Technology Readiness Level (MTRL) framework (Figure 13).

Figure 13: SWForum.eu Webinars – MTRL

Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, these webinars successfully ensured that crucial knowledge sharing and engagement could continue. SWForum.eu also provided the community with valuable information regarding thematic topics such as Open Source Software, Software technologies and standards, and DevOps Innovation, spanning from October 2022 to April 2023 (Figure 14).

Figure 14: SWForum.eu Webinars – Thematic Topics

These webinars have played a pivotal role in fostering collaboration, facilitating the exchange of knowledge, and keeping the software community informed about the latest developments. They have contributed to the growth and advancement of the software technology landscape, empowering professionals with valuable insights and tools to drive successful software technology projects forward (Table 5).

Figure 15 shows some of the live Twitter coverages during the MTRL and thematic webinars.

Figure 15: SWForum.eu Webinars – Twitter Live Coverage

Table 5: List of SWForum.eu Webinars – Impacts and Outreach results

Workshop, Date	Participants	Pageviews	Video Views
Market & Technology Readiness Levels, 26 May 2021 [13]	43	409	267
Understanding criteria for optimal self-assessment of project outcomes using Market & Technology Readiness Levels, 27 Oct 2021 [14]	41	135	53
SWForum.eu Webinar: Leveraging OS technologies for better services in the European software ecosystem, 10 Oct 2022	36	321	33
Software Technologies & Standards: Enabling Interoperability and Innovation, 21 Feb 2023	43	400	22

DevOps Innovation in Practice: New lifecycle processes, new applications, 20 Apr 2023	35	305	38
Understanding the Impact of MTRL Assessments, 5 Jun 2023	20	118	Recording is not available

3.1.3.1 Community

These webinars garnered significant interest from around the globe, attracting more than 200 participants representing 23 countries.

Figure 16: Global impact of SWForum.eu webinars

Thematic webinars concluded with joint recommendations from invited EU-funded projects.

3.1.3.2 Engagement

A series of campaigns have been carried out. The impact of these is summarised in Table 6.

Table 6: SWForum.eu Workshops: Engagement campaigns, activities and impacts

Engagement Campaign	Activities	Impact
Agenda definition and logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Personalised email invitation ☐ One-on-one calls to plan sessions and participation ☐ Shaping of different sessions, spanning presentations, panels ☐ Rehearsal calls 	A total of 12 EC-funded projects and 5 experts from the European Commission, industries, and academies were engaged to contribute to the agenda shaping and participate as speakers or panellists in the SWForum.eu-webinars.
Promotional campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Event branding identity ☐ Event communication packages ☐ Social media post creation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Increase of 86.67% in terms of unique visits to the events page ☐ Total of 1.7K event page views

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Personalised email invitation ▣ Dedicated newsletters ▣ Social media coverages for Pre, Post and during event 	Continuous social media engagement with growth in followers
Post-webinar campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Recorded webinar ▣ Joint recommendation reports ▣ Project Spotlight featuring the synergy with SWForum.eu ▣ Social media report promotion ▣ Newsletters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ 3 recommendation reports were published ▣ Report gained over 200 views and 187 downloads

3.2 Software development organisations and industry players

Several European software industries are actively collaborating with SWForum.eu to enhance Europe’s global software standing since the first organised SWForum.eu workshop was held in March 2021. By partnering with SWForum.eu, not only EU-funded projects but also industry experts and organisations gain a platform to promote their interests, connect with representatives from various sectors, influence software strategy, and engage with policymakers.

Various activities were organised in order to foster cross-sector relationships and exchange innovative ideas for the future of the software community in Europe.

3.2.1 Open Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability

SWForum.eu played a crucial role in the communication and dissemination efforts of the “Open Source Workshops on Computing Sustainability” event organised by DG DIGIT and DG CONNECT of the European Commission, ensuring its success and broad engagement. The event was held physically on 2 December 2022 in Brussels (Figure 17), featuring 12 workshops focused on various open source topics relating to computing and sustainability (Figure 18).

Figure 17: Open Source Workshop – Photo Gallery

Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability	
Friday, 02 December 2022 – Albert Borschette Congress Centre (CCAB)	
08:30	Registration
09:30	Welcome and opening session (Room 0A) Pearse O'Donohue, Director CNECT.DDGL.E - Future Networks Natalia Aristimuño Pérez, Director of Digital Services, DIGIT.D
09:25	Keynote Speeches (Room 0A) John Davis (BSC - Barcelona Supercomputing Centre) Maria Dahlhage (DIGG - Swedish Agency for Digital Government)
10:00	Parallel Workshop Session 1
10:00	WS1.1 - Open Source Processors for the Cloud Continuum (Room 0A) Chair: Luis C. Buzquets Pérez, EC-CONNECT. Panelists: John Davis (BSC), Roger Espasa (Semidynamics), Andrea Acquaviva (University of Bologna), Olof Kindgren (Qamcom Technology AB and FOSSI Foundation), Patrick Pype (NXP and RISC-V Open Source Working Group), Craig Prunty (SiPearl)
11:30	WS1.2 - The role of OSS in Artificial Intelligence enabled systems: Speeding the AI adoption through OSS (Room 0B) Chair: Miguel Estera (TECNALLA). Panelists: Silvia Castellvi (IDSA), Tim Löweweyhn (Bonseyes), Kerstin Bach (NTNU), Danilo Ardagna (Politecnico di Milano - AI-SPRINT project)
12:00	WS1.3 - Building Sustainable Open Source Ecosystems for an Interoperable Europe (Room 1A) Chair: Leontina Sandu (Head of Interoperability Unit, DIGIT D2), assisted by Monika Sowinska (DIGIT). Panelists: Maria Dahlhage (DIGG - Swedish Agency for Digital Government), Clare Dillon (Executive Director, InnerSource Commons), Jiri Marek (Open Cities - Otevřená města - Board Member), Sachiko Muto (Chairman at OpenForum Europe, Senior Researcher at RISE), Maximilian Strotmann (Member of Commissioner Hahn's Cabinet)
12:00	WS1.4 - Identifying, fixing and managing critical open source software used by European Public Services (Room 0C) Chair: Miguel Díez Blanco (EC OSPO Team Lead, DIGIT B3.002), assisted by Saranjit Arora (EC OSPO). Panelists: Camille Moulin (Inno3), Dirk-Willem van Gulik (Founder and first president of the Apache Software Foundation), Gaël Blondelle (Eclipse foundation), Michiel Leenaars (NLnet Foundation), Roman Shaposhnik (VP of Legal affairs, Apache Software Foundation), Peter Ganten (University, OSBA)
11:30	Coffee Break
12:00	Parallel Workshop Session 2
12:00	WS2.1 - Open Source Software and Cloud Services and Applications: On the way to more interoperable cloud services (Room 0A) Chair: Leire Orue-Echevarria (EC CONNECT). Panelists: Josef Urban (Nokia Bell Labs and NNESSI), Frank Karltitschek (NextCloud), Astor Nummelin Carlberg (OpenForumEurope), Maria Fazio (University of Messina), Alberto P. Marti (OpenNebula)
13:30	WS2.2 - The potential of the symbiosis of Quantum Computing and OSS: Development of quantum computing OS algorithms and software (Room 0B) Chair: Fanny Bouton (OVHCloud). Panelists: Koen Bertels (QBE), Jean Senellart (Quandela), Robert Wille (TU Munich), Christian Gamrat (CEA-QUICATS project)
12:00	WS2.3 - Encouraging open-source business applications reuse via the creation of an EU wide Applications Catalogue for European Public Services (Room 1A) Chair: Evangelos Tsavalopoulos (Head of Sector, DIGIT B3.002), assisted by Saranjit Arora (EC OSPO). Panelists: Clementine Yalayer (Gartner), Deniz Ozketen (FOSSEPS Project - Sopra Steria), Diego Calvo de Náj (OSB Alliance), Leonardo Favario (Team Digitale), Stefano Zucchiroli (Software Heritage), Fabio Bonelli (Team Digitale).
13:30	WS2.4 - Exploring how the European public sector can cooperate and act together to solve the key open source issues they face (Room 0C) Chair: Gijis Hillenius (DIGIT), assisted by Miguel Díez Blanco (EC OSPO Team Lead, DIGIT B3.002). Panelists: Boris Van Hoytema (Foundation for Public Code), Daniel Melin (Skatteverket - Swedish Tax Agency), Frederik Blachetta (Dataport, Germany), Daniele Pagani (SIGI), Maria Dahlhage (DIGG - Swedish Agency for Digital Government), Joël Lambilliotte (IMIO).
13:30	Lunch Break
14:30	Parallel Workshop Session 3
14:30	WS3.1 - Open standards and industrial use for Open Source: Leveraging the sustainability of Open Source projects and increasing competition and interoperability between different steps in value-chains (Room 0A) Chair: John Favaro (Trust-IT - StandICT.eu). Panelists: Simon Phipps (Meshed Insights), Michael Plagge (ECLIPSE Foundation), Luca Alloatti (Free Silicon Foundation), Clara Perzuela (FIWARE Foundation), Alex Sander (Free Software Foundation Europe)
16:00	WS3.2 - Towards a trustworthy and secure ecosystem of OSS: Increasing the reliability and adoption of OSS projects (Room 0B) Chair: James Galand-Jones (EC-CONNECT). Panelists: Sebastian Prokch (TUDELFT - FASTEN project), David Wheeler (Linux Foundation - OpenSSF), Volkmar Lotz (SAP), Maika Fehrenbach (EC-CONNECT).
16:00	WS3.3 - Agreeing, measuring and encouraging organisational contribution to the open source ecosystem (Room 1A) Chair: Saranjit Arora (EC OSPO), assisted by Miguel Díez Blanco (EC OSPO Team Lead, DIGIT B3.002). Panelists: Bastien Guerry (Etalab/DINUM), Leslie Hawthorn (Red Hat), Sachiko Muto (OpenForumEurope), Timo Levi (T-Systems), Tobie Langel (Senior Fellow, Omidyar Network), Italo Vignoli (Document Foundation)
16:00	WS3.4 - Exploring practical solutions to ensure long term sustainability of open source software (Room 0C) Chair: Chrysanthi Giortsoy (Dy Head of Unit, B3), assisted by Gijis Hillenius (DIGIT). Panelists: Fiona Krakenbürger (Sovereign fund), Jarek Potluc (PMC member of Apache Airflow), Matthieu Faure (Adifalco), Paolo Vecchi (Ministry of the Economy - Luxembourg), Stefane Fernigier (CNIL/APPELL), Stefan Zosel (Cagemin - Global Public Sector)
16:00	Closing session Pierre Chastanet (Head of Unit Cloud & Software-DG CONNECT, European Commission)
16:35	and next steps

Figure 18: Open Source Workshop – Agenda

Leveraging its extensive network and expertise, SWForum.eu successfully raised awareness about the event, reaching a diverse range of stakeholders within the software industry. By actively promoting the event, SWForum.eu facilitated meaningful discussions, knowledge-sharing, and the widespread dissemination of valuable insights and innovative ideas. Through its involvement, SWForum.eu significantly increased the event's visibility, fostering collaboration and driving the adoption of sustainable practices within the open-source computing community.

In addition to the organisational role, the SWForum.eu team actively took on rapporteur tasks during each session of the workshops. Working closely with the European Commission, they gathered valuable information and insights from the discussions, presentations, and

interactions that took place. Their dedicated efforts aimed to provide comprehensive reports capturing the outcomes and key findings of each workshop. By collaborating directly with the European Commission, SWForum.eu ensures that the reports are accurate, reliable, and reflect the valuable contributions made by participants. These reports serve as a valuable resource for stakeholders and decision-makers, enabling them to gain a deeper understanding of the topics discussed and informing future actions and initiatives in the realm of open source sustainability and computing.

Figure 19 shows the cover and back images of the report created from this event, which have been shared with the commission.

Figure 19: Open Source Workshop – Reports

3.2.1.1 Engagement

A series of campaigns have been carried out. The impact of these is summarised in Table 7.

Table 7: Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability – Engagement campaigns, activities and impacts

Engagement Campaign	Activities	Impact
Agenda definition and logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Official event page creation ❑ Personalised email invitation to projects, experts and policy makers ❑ One-on-one calls to plan sessions and participation ❑ Shaping of different sessions, spanning presentations, panels 	A total of 200 live attendees with 86 from the European Commission, industries, and academies were engaged to contribute to the agenda shaping and participate as speakers or panellists.
Promotional campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Personalised event branding identity ❑ Event communication packages: Roll-up banner, Agenda, Speaker banners ❑ Social media post creation ❑ Personalised email invitation ❑ Dedicated newsletters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Increase of 86.67% in terms of unique visits to the events page ❑ Total of 1.7K page views ❑ Continuous social media engagement with growth in followers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Social media coverages for Pre, Post and during event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Featured on HADEA website [15], European Commission News [16]
Post-webinar campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Recorded webinar ❑ Joint recommendation reports ❑ Project Spotlight featuring the synergy with SWForum.eu ❑ Social media report promotion ❑ Newsletters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ 3 graphically designed workshop reports were created and shared with the European Commission

3.2.2 Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT

The OpenContinuum consortium, together with the UNLOCK-CEI and SWForum projects and with the support of the European Commission DG CNECT E.2 and E.4 Units, is hosting a two-day physical event titled "Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT." This event is part of the European Cloud, Edge, and IoT Continuum initiative and will be held at the Claridge in Brussels, Belgium. The event aims to bring together experts, stakeholders, and projects involved in the computing continuum domain to facilitate discussions, collaboration, and knowledge sharing on the latest advancements and challenges in the field.

Juncal Alonso (SWForum.eu Coordinator) has contributed to the discussion on strategic R&I roadmaps. Moreover, Juncal together with John Favaro (Communications Lead) chaired the panel discussion on "Software models, tools and processes for the continuum".

3.2.2.1 Engagement

A series of campaigns have been carried out. The impact of these is summarised in Table 8.

Table 8: Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT – Engagement campaigns, activities and impacts

Engagement Campaign	Activities	Impact
Agenda definition and logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ One-on-one calls to plan sessions and participation ❑ Shaping of different sessions, spanning presentations, panels ❑ Rapporteur task 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ A total of 100 live attendees
Promotional campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Support with the social promotion ❑ Social media post creation ❑ Included in the newsletters ❑ Live social media coverage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Engaged with 44 EU-funded projects

3.3 European Software and Open-source Experts

SWForum.eu has engaged with European software and open-source experts to foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, influence policy, and promote innovation in the software industry. By connecting with these experts, SWForum.eu taps into their expertise, enables networking, and drives advancements in software engineering and standards. The objective of the outreach is to cultivate a dynamic ecosystem that brings value to the European software community.

3.3.1 Open Call for Fellowship Applications

SWForum.eu is an instrument to streamline the cross-fertilisation programme through the Open Call for Fellowship platform hosted on the website.

A simple graphical layout, entry points and step-by-step instructions provide clear sign-posting for applicants or those interested in applying. The page title “Call for Fellowship Applications” is used to make it clearer that funding can be accessed on this page [17]. The programme has engaged with six experts from variety of backgrounds and institutions, selected to cover a broad spectrum of domains and experience within research, software technologies, digital infrastructures, cybersecurity and open source (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Open Call for Fellowship Programme – Social media promotion and key result

A dedicated page (Figure 21) was created to showcase the selected fellowship experts [18] who made significant contributions to the active and engaging Online SWForum. These experts shared their expertise through insightful blog posts.

Figure 21: SWForum.eu Fellowship Programme - Webpage

3.3.1.1 Engagement

A series of campaigns have been carried out. The impact of these is summarised in the table below.

Table 9: Open Call for Fellowship Programme – Engagement campaigns, activities and impacts

Engagement Campaign	Activities	Impact
Programme definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❏ Website page creation ❏ Procedure of application ❏ Programme Branding identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❏ Received 13 applications ❏ Total of 1.9K views per user
Promotional campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❏ Social media post creation ❏ Included in the newsletters ❏ Personalised email invitation ❏ Communication pack 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❏ A total of 6 selected experts ❏ Achieved 2.5K impressions for the live Twitter promotion

3.3.1 Online SW Forum

The SWForum.eu Online Forum [19] offers an online forum for users to actively participate in discussions related to software, cybersecurity, and digital infrastructure. Although not initially included in the Grant Agreement, the consortium recognized the importance of virtual community-building measures amidst the COVID-19 crisis. As a result, an online discussion forum was introduced, utilising the existing Forum+ facilities developed by Trust-IT (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Online SWForum Discussion – Webpage

To support the SWForum.eu project and foster a sustainable European forum, the SWForum.eu Fellowship Programme has been established. This program aims to bring together stakeholders, including scientific researchers, providers, developers, operators, and policymakers, in the fields of software technologies, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. By raising awareness and contributing to the competitiveness of the European software industry, the Fellowship Programme ensures the project maintains a strong international presence in the software technology landscape.

Our efforts yielded a collection of 71 insightful and valuable pieces of content contributed by experts. These contributions have played a significant role in shaping the future of the software industry in Europe, covering a broad range of topics, as shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Online SWForum – Published Blogs

Forum Topics	Fellows						
	Alfonso Ferreira	Apostolos Kritikos	Joao Costa	Luca Benedetto	Martin Higgins	Merve Öper	Total
Advanced Digital Skills				1			1

AI and Machine Learning				1		1	2
Big Data and HPC						1	1
Computing Continuum					1		1
Cyber-physical systems					1		1
Cybersecurity	3		1		7	1	12
Digital Infrastructure	6				2		8
Ethical Computing						1	1
Green Computing			2				2
Open Source			2	1			3
Software Development Life	1			2		3	6
Software Operations	1						1
Software Technology	2	6	8	8	2	6	32

To generate greater interest and engagement across the software community, the blogs were strategically promoted on the SWForum.eu website through a dedicated news piece. Additionally, various social media channels were utilised to amplify the reach and visibility of these blogs. By leveraging both the website and social media platforms, a wider audience was attracted, allowing the valuable insights and discussions within the blogs to reach a broader community of software professionals and enthusiasts (Figure 23 and Figure 24).

Figure 23: Online SW-Forum Discussion – Website promotions

Figure 24: Online SW-Forum Discussion – Social media promotions

3.3.1.1 Engagement

A series of campaigns have been carried out. The impact of these is summarised in Table 11.

Table 11: Open Call for Fellowship Programme – Engagement campaigns, activities and impacts

Engagement Campaign	Activities	Impact
Programme definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Website page creation ☐ Forum+ procedures ☐ Programme Branding identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Received 71 blogs ☐ 105 registered Forum users
Promotional campaign	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ News and social media post creation ☐ Included in the newsletters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Gained 4.5K impressions on social media promotions ☐ Achieved 4.7K impressions for the live Twitter promotion

DRAFT

4 Communication and Dissemination Impacts

SWForum.eu's communication partner, Trust-IT Services, has strictly cooperated with all partners to maximise the visibility and awareness of the project's main results and widely disseminate its outcomes. In particular, in order to achieve this, SWForum.eu's communication and dissemination focused on the following activities:

- ▣ Targeted messages to stakeholder groups (SGs);
- ▣ Implementation of SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Timely) campaigns for social media channels
- ▣ a minor revamp of the SWForum.eu website, including an updated version of different sections such as the Online SW-Forum discussion, assets and services, etc., to better showcase the results and activities delivered in the project framework;
- ▣ Participation and organisation of events.

Moreover, to support the communication campaigns of SWForum.eu, a diverse set of tools and channels are utilised to ensure a multichannel approach to reaching each stakeholder.

The impact of the communication and dissemination activities was monitored throughout the entire lifespan of the projects with defined KPIs whose values are summarised in the following sections.

4.1 Website

Over the lifespan of the project, the website went through two main revamps, at M7 and several small adjustments, that aimed to ensure a pleasant user experience (UX) with enhanced structure, new pages that aim to streamline the communication and outreach for the SWForum.eu.

The SWForum.eu website serves as a central platform for showcasing the key assets, results, and analyses generated within the project. It provides a comprehensive and easily accessible repository of valuable information. In addition, the team has implemented upgrades to the Online SW-Forum page, focusing on enhancing the user experience. These improvements ensure that users can navigate and engage with the platform more efficiently, enabling them to make the most of the available resources and actively participate in discussions (Figure 25).

Figure 25: SWForum.eu Website Structure - New

4.1.1 Website Performance

SWForum.eu website attained satisfactory web traffic as shown in the figures and tables below. The website performance is tracked on a dedicated website dashboard that allows a quicker analysis of the impact of data coming from Google Analytics. The main website achievements are summarised as follows:

- **Website statistics.** Critical figures provide valuable insights into a website's performance, user behaviours, and engagement. They include metrics such as visitor traffic, page views, unique visitors, bounce rate, and conversion rate. These statistics help website owners make data-driven decisions to optimise the user experience and achieve their goals. Monitoring is done using Google Analytics to track user interactions and behaviours, providing essential figures like user count, page views, and average engagement rate. Low bounce rates indicate meaningful user engagement with the website's content.

Table 12: SWForum.eu Website Performance – Statistics Update

Website statistics	Value at Mar 2022 (M18)	Value at Jun 2023 (M33)	Improvement Rate from M18 vs M33
Number of unique users	1309	3780	65.37%
Number of sessions	2488	7548	67.02%
Number of pageviews	14789	33167	51.41%
Average bounce rate	62.27%	59.16%	55.42%

Figure 26: SWForum.eu Website Statistics – Usage Data

Website acquisition. Direct access is the primary entry point for users to the website, indicating a significant number of recurring visitors who directly enter the website URL or search for it on major search engines. Organic search is another prominent source of traffic, indicating a strong SEO presence for important keywords. Referrals from external websites and social media also contribute to productive traffic sources.

Figure 27: SWForum.eu Website Statistics – Pageviews

Countries. The majority of website visitors originate from Italy, Spain, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and Belgium. This signifies a positive response, indicating that the research conducted by SWForum.eu is valued and utilized not only by European partners but also by non-EU countries. Figure 28 displays the top 10 countries that visit the SWForum.eu website.

Figure 28: SWForum.eu Website Traffic by Country

4.2 Social media

Social media platforms, including Twitter (@SWforuEU), LinkedIn (@SWForumEU), and YouTube (@swforumeuproject), play a crucial role in strengthening SWForum's online presence, facilitating communication, and engaging with target stakeholder groups. These channels are utilised to execute SMART campaigns, allowing for continuous monitoring of performance. Through social media, SWForum.eu promotes various content such as videos, webinars, workshops, and its participation in third-party events. This strategic utilisation of social media channels ensures maximum outreach, impact, and community engagement, while also highlighting publications and news of interest to the ecosystem. Each social media channel serves a unique purpose within the overall communication strategy, as explained in the following paragraphs.

4.2.1 Twitter

Twitter serves as a dynamic platform for real-time updates, news dissemination, and event promotion, showcasing the progress and insights gained as the project evolves. It plays a vital role in communication campaigns, including event promotion, showcasing project advancements, and utilising Twitter cards to highlight project partners' scientific perspectives on specific aspects. The platform excels in providing comprehensive coverage of live events through "live tweeting," ensuring timely updates and key takeaways for those unable to attend in person. Additionally, Twitter is frequently utilised to repurpose important project materials and outputs, enhancing their visibility and accessibility within the community. Concrete examples of Twitter's impact are presented in Figure 29.

Figure 29: SWForum.eu Twitter Performance

Table 13 summarises the Twitter's main achievements and shows the social media tracker use for regular monitoring using the dashboard.

Table 13: SWForum.eu Twitter Performance Update

Twitter statistics	Value at Mar 2022 (M18)	Value at Jun 2023 (M33)	Improvement Rate from M18 vs M33
Followers	250	388	35.6 %
Tweets	119	920	87.1%
Likes	840	1383	39.3%
Retweets	774	1163	33.4%
Impressions	92,910	180,569	48.5%

Unfortunately, we are unable to provide final Twitter statistics on the number of retweets and likes at this time due to ongoing issues and limitations with Twitter's data availability [20].

Figure 30: SWForum.eu Dashboard: Twitter Engagement

4.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn serves as a valuable platform to share regular updates, promote activities, engage with members, and expand the professional community. It is utilized for SMART campaigns to generate interest and drive participation in SWForum.eu events, such as workshops and

webinars, where the latest developments are showcased. Additionally, LinkedIn plays a crucial role in onboarding new stakeholders who are relevant to SWForum.eu and inviting them to participate in relevant events and webinars.

The figures and table below showcase the key achievements in terms of LinkedIn outreach activities.

Table 14: SWForum.eu LinkedIn Performance

LinkedIn statistics	Value at Mar 2022 (M18)	Value at Jun 2023 (M33)	Improvement Rate from M18 vs M33
Followers	899	1153	22.1%
Post	78	170	54.1%
Reactions	77	435	82.3%
Shares	183	283	35.3%
Impressions	6813	15221	55.2%

Figure 31: SWForum.eu LinkedIn Performance, from 4 July 2022 – 3 July 2023

Figure 32: SWForum.eu Dashboard: Twitter Engagement

Its unique value lies in the ability to search for individuals based on specific job types and geographic areas, enabling targeted outreach to specific stakeholder groups. By connecting with these individuals, they can be invited to events and receive updates through the company page, ensuring their engagement and involvement in SWForum.eu activities.

Figure 33: SWForum.eu LinkedIn Followers' Demographics by Industry and job function

4.3 Graphically-designed materials

A detailed overview of the project's Communication Kit, visual identity elements, and graphics collateral can be found in deliverable D4.1 [2]. The aim of developing a harmonious branding strategy was to create a recognizable graphic pattern that could be consistently used by the entire Consortium across multiple channels, effectively connecting back to SWForum.eu.

Figure 34: Examples of graphic banners

The team also created informative digital reports as part of the graphic materials. One notable example is the post-webinar reports that showcase the main results achieved from the organisation of the SWForum.eu webinars on thematic topics. The digital reports show in a compelling and intuitive way the main objectives of the events, the attendance rate, and the stakeholders engagement.

The digitally designed reports were published both in dedicated sections on the SWForum.eu webinar pages and publication page, which are uploaded to the project's Zenodo [21] account to guarantee complete accessibility, in compliance with Open Access principles.

The reports account for, at the moment of writing, nearly 700 visualisations, both on Zenodo and on the website, and 187 downloads.

Figure 35: Examples of graphic banners

4.4 Videos

Videos play a crucial role in engaging with targeted stakeholders and delivering complex information in a digestible format. The SWForum.eu project has produced a collection of videos, primarily created by in-house specialists, which are housed on the SWforumEU YouTube channel [22]. The channel features 20 videos across six (6) playlists and has garnered a total of 845 views.

Figure 36: SWForum.eu Video – Webpage

On 27 June 2023, a final video capturing the highlights of the *Way Forward* Workshop was recorded. The video is now available for viewing on the SWForum.eu YouTube channel. Also, short GIF videos that are used for social media promotions.

Figure 37: Sample of short GIF video for social media promotion

4.5 Newsletters

Newsletters are a powerful tool for raising awareness and providing valuable information to stakeholders. The SWForum project has developed a branded newsletter with a user-friendly framework to engage readers and encourage action. Throughout the project, 20 newsletters have been issued, proving to be effective in engaging the community with an open rate of nearly 40%.

Table 15: Newsletter performance

Newsletter	20 newsletter releases
Subscribers	153 subscribers
Open rate	39.1% with a total of 756 Opens
Click rate	32.5% with a total of 155 Clicks
Click-to-open rate	18.8% (Jun 2023)

Note: The average email open rate should be between 15-25%. The average click-through rate should be about 2.5%. Your average click-to-open rate should be between 20-30%

Figure 38: SWForum.eu Newsletter issues

4.6 Events and Webinars

SWForum.eu executed its campaigns on events, project outputs, and assets with a SMART approach, ensuring they are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely. To effectively engage with a global target audience, the following activities were implemented as part of the engagement campaign:

- ❑ **Agenda:** Collaborating closely with the consortium, we meticulously crafted the timing and goals for each webinar, defining the main categories of discussion and setting audience expectations.
- ❑ **Registration and logistics:** The SWForum.eu consortium managed the registration process, the Zoom platform, and provided technical support throughout the event. We conducted a rehearsal beforehand to ensure smooth slides and address any housekeeping matters.
- ❑ **Engagement campaigns:** Our webinars catered to three types: technological, topic-oriented, and project-specific. We capitalized on webinar channels that reached like-minded communities, such as CORDIS and the Synergy Software R&I projects. See Annex II for the list of project synergies.
- ❑ **Promotional campaign:** We designed a branded event banner, sent personalised email invitations to our community, and launched a special edition newsletter and social media campaign to maximise visibility. We also communicated with registered participants via email shortly before the event. During the event, we live-tweeted to keep followers engaged and informed.
- ❑ **Post-event activities:** Following the webinars, we prepared an official post-event report summarising the main outputs and recommendations, which was promoted on open-source platforms like Zenodo and related project websites. We promptly sent thank-you messages to participants and key speakers within 48 hours, including the recorded video for those who wanted to revisit or missed the event.
- ❑ **Video recordings:** All the recordings of individual sessions were published a week after the event on the event page, which was uploaded on SWForum.eu YouTube channel.

Through these comprehensive engagement strategies, SWForum.eu strives to maximise the impact of its campaigns, ensuring valuable insights and knowledge are effectively shared with the community. See the list of events in Annex I.

5 Conclusions

SWForum.eu continuously evolved its dissemination and communications strategy over the duration of the project, responding to a series of risks (COVID-19 pandemic) and opportunities (a revamped Fellowship Programme) that presented themselves in with innovations and a flexible toolbox of communications tools to fit the occasions as they presented themselves.

The platform that was utilized as the foundation for outreach has become a sustainable legacy of the project, both in terms of content (especially the many posts made by the Fellows, but also the many presentations in high-level workshops and deliverables of the project) and in extended facilities that are destined to become products (such as the Forum+ facility that was enriched over the course of the project).

The project became an effective testbed for innovations in outreach to the software engineering community in Europe, and has made its contribution to the strengthening of that community going forward.

6 References

- [1] SWForum Consortium, «D4.2 - Report on dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement – v1 (M18),» 2022.
- [2] SWForum Consortium, «D4.1 Plan for dissemination, communication & stakeholder engagement (M3),» 2020.
- [3] SWForum Consortium, «D2.6 – Project Radar Landscape Analysis V1 (M15),» 2021.
- [4] SWForum Consortium, «Project Hub - Spotlight,» [En línea].
- [5] SWForum.eu Consortium, «D2.3 - Cross-fertilization worksop report - v3,» 2023.
- [6] SWForum Consortium, «First SWForum .eu Workshop on Trustworthy Software and Open Source,» March 2021. [En línea].
- [7] SWForum Consortium, «Second SWForum.eu Workshop: Research Challenges, Collaboration, and Coordination in European Software Engineering Projects,» June 2021. [En línea].
- [8] SWForum Consortium, «First SWForum.eu Sustainability Workshop,» 2022 January. [En línea].
- [9] SWForum Consortium, «WEGreen - SWForum and HUB4CLOUD Workshop on Engineering Green and Sustainable Software in the Computing Continuum,» September 2022. [En línea].
- [10] SWForum Consortium, «Open Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability,» December 2022. [En línea].
- [11] SWForum Consortium, «The First Fast Coontinuum Workshop,» April 2023. [En línea].
- [12] SWForum Consortium, «SWForum.eu The Way Forward: Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering,» June 2023. [En línea].
- [13] SWForum Consortium, «SWForum.eu Webinar: Market & Technology Readiness Levels,» May 2021. [En línea].
- [14] SWForum Consortium, October 2021. [En línea].
- [15] European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), «Join the Webinar “DevOps Innovation in Practice: New lifecycle processes, new applications” on 20 April 2023 and meet several EU-funded projects,» April 2023. [En línea].
- [16] European Commission, «EC Open Source Workshops - Computing and Sustainability, 2 December 2022,» October 2022. [En línea].

- [17] SWForum Website, «Call for Fellowship Application,» [En línea]. Available: <https://swforum.eu/call-fellowship-applications>.
- [18] SWForum Consortium, «Fellowship Experts,» [En línea]. Available: <https://swforum.eu/fellowship-experts>.
- [19] SWForum Consortium, «Online SW-Forum,» [En línea]. Available: <https://www.swforum.eu/online-sw-forum>.
- [20] NBC NEWS, «NBC NEWS featured tech news on Twitter's chaotic weekend ends with more questions than answers,» [En línea]. Available: <https://www.nbcnews.com/tech/tech-news/twitter-changes-tweetdeck-rate-limit-rcna92369>.
- [21] SWForum Consortium, «SWForum Zenodo Community,» [En línea]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/communities/swforum/>.
- [22] SWForum Consortium, «YTC@swforumeuproject,» [En línea].

ANNEX I – List of Events

Table 16 contains the list of organised and participated events of SWForum.eu team from M19-M33.

Table 16: Events (M19-M33) – organised and participated events

Events	Date, Location	Category	Typology
ICSR 2022	15-17 Jun 2022, Online	3rd Party Event	Conference
WEGreen Workshop (in collaboration with HUB4CLOUD)	15 Sep 2022, Hybrid, Izola, Slovenia	Co-located event	Workshop
SWForum.eu Webinar: Leveraging OS technologies for better services in the European software ecosystem	10 Oct 2022, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Webinar
Open Source Workshop for Computing and Sustainability (in collaboration with the European Commission)	2 December 2022, Brussels, Belgium	SWForum.eu organised event	Workshop
Software Technologies and Standards: Enabling Interoperability and Innovation	21 Feb 2023, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Webinar
The First Fast Continuum Workshop (Joint workshop with PIACERE and AI-SPRINT in conjunction with ICPE 2023)	16 April 2023, Coimbra, Portugal	Co-located event	Workshop
DevOps Innovation in Practice: New lifecycle processes, new applications	20 Apr 2023, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Webinar
Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT	10-11 May 2023, Brussels, Belgium	3rd Party Event	Workshop
Understanding the Impact of MTRL Assessments	5 Jun 2023, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Webinar
SWForum.eu The Way Forward: Workshop on Future Challenges in Software Engineering	27 June 2023, Milan, Italy	SWForum.eu organised event	Workshop

ANNEX II – List of Project Synergies

Table 17 reflects the project synergies of SWForum.eu during the project lifetime.

Table 17: EC Project Synergies (M1-M33)

ProjectAcronym	Project Name
AC3	Agile and Cognitive Cloud edge Continuum management
ACES	Autopoietic Cognitive Edge-cloud Services
ACCORDION	Adaptive edge/cloud compute and network continuum over a heterogeneous sparse edge infrastructure to support nextgen applications
ADRA-e	AI, Data and Robotics ecosystem
AERO	Accelerated EuRopean cLOud
aerOS	Autonomous, scalable, trustworthy, intelligent European meta Operating System for the IoT edge-cloud continuum
AI-SPRINT	Artificial Intelligence in Secure Privacy-preserving computing coNTinuum
AI4PublicPolicy	Automated, Transparent Citizen-Centric Public Policy Making based on Trusted Artificial Intelligence
ARTICONF	smart social media eCOsystem in a blockchain Federated environment
ASSIST-IoT	Architecture for Scalable, Self-*, human-centric, Intelligent, Secure, and Tactile next generation IoT
BLUE-CLOUD	Blue-Cloud: Piloting innovative services for Marine Research & the Blue Economy
Bonseyes	Platform for Open Development of Systems of Artificial Intelligence
CEA-QUCATS	Quantum Flagship Coordination Action and Support
CHARITY	Cloud for Holography and Cross Reality
CloudButton	Serverless Data Analytics Platform
CloudSkin	Adaptive virtualization for AI-enabled Cloud-edge Continuum
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralised Edge Cloud Orchestration
COGNIFOG	AI-empowered Edge Cloud Continuum for self-aware cognitive computing environments
COSMOS	DevOps for Complex Cyber-physical Systems
CyberSec4Europe	Cyber Security for Europe
Cyberwatching.eu	The European watch on cybersecurity privacy
DataCloud	ENABLING BIG DATA PIPELINE LIFECYCLE ON THE COMPUTING CONTINUUM
De-RISC	De-RISC: Dependable Real-time Infrastructure for Safety-critical Computer
DECENTER	Decentralised technologies for orchestrated cloud-to-edge intelligence
DECICE	Device-Edge-Cloud Intelligent Collaboration framEwork

DECODER	Developer Companion for Documented and annotated code Reference
DESTINI	Smart Data ProcESSing and SysTems of Deep INsight
EDGELESS	Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing
ELEGANT	Secure and Seamless Edge-to-Cloud Analytics
EnergyShield	Integrated Cybersecurity Solution for the Vulnerability Assessment, Monitoring and Protection of Critical Energy Infrastructures
EOSC-SYNERGY	European Open Science Cloud - Expanding Capacities by building Capabilities
EUCloudEdgeIoT	Unlocking the Cloud Edge IoT demand potential in Europe
ExpANDS	EOSC Photon and Neutron Data Services
FAIR4Health	Improving Health Research in EU through FAIR Data
FASTEN	Fine-Grained Analysis of Software Ecosystems as Networks
FISHY	A coordinated framework for cyber resilient supply chain systems over complex ICT infrastructures
FLUIDOS	Flexible, scaLable and secUre decentralizEd OperatiNg
FOCETA	FOUNDATIONS FOR CONTINUOUS ENGINEERING OF TRUSTWORTHY AUTONOMY
FogProtect	Protecting Sensitive Data in the Computing Continuum
FOSSEPS	Free and Open Source Software Solutions for European Public Services
GN4-3N	Horizon 2020: H2020-SGA-INFRA-GEANT-2018 Topic [b] Increase of Long-Term Backbone Capacity
Graph Massivizer	Extreme and Sustainable Graph Processing for Urgent Societal Challenges in Europe
HSbooster.eu	Standardisation Booster for H2020 & HE research results
HUB4CLOUD	The European Cloud Computing Hub to grow a sustainable and comprehensive ecosystem
ICOS	Towards a functional continuum operating system
INCODE	Programming Platform for Intelligent Collaborative Deployments over Heterogeneous Edge-IoT Environments
INGENIOUS	Next-GENeration IoT sOlutions for the Universal Supply chain
INTELLIOT	Intelligent, distributed, human-centered and trustworthy IoT environments
InterQ	Interlinked Process, Product and Data Quality framework for Zero-Defect Manufacturing
IOT-NGIN	Next Generation IoT as part of Next Generation Internet
IoTAC	Security by design IoT development and certificate framework with front-end access control
MEDINA	Security framework to achieve a continuous audit-based certification in compliance with the EU-wide cloud security certification scheme

MLSysOps	Machine Learning for Autonomic System Operation in the Heterogeneous Edge-Cloud Continuum
MORPHEMIC	Modelling and Orchestrating heterogeneous Resources and Polymorphic applications for Holistic Execution and adaptation of Models In the Cloud
NEBULOUS	A meta operating system for brokering hyper-distributed applications on cloud computing continuums
NEMO	Next Generation Meta Operating System
NEPHELE	eNd to End scalable and dynamically reconfigurable oPtical archItecture for application-awarE SDN cLoud datacentErs
NGI Ledger GeneCosent	Next Generation Internet Ledger
OASEES	Open Autonomous programmable cloud appS & smart EdgE Sensors
ONTOCHAIN	Trusted, traceable and transparent ontological knowledge on blockchain
OpenAIRE	OpenAIRE
OpenCUBE	Open-Source Cloud-Based Services on EPI Systems
OpenSwarm	Orchestration and Programming ENergy-aware and collaborative Swarms With AI-powered Reliable Methods
PHYSICS	Optimized hybrid space-time service continuum in FAAS
PIACERE	Programming trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a sECuRE framework
Policy Cloud	Policy Management through technologies across the complete data lifecycle on cloud environment
RADON	Rational decomposition and orchestration for serverless computing
ReachOut	The Beta Testing Campaign Platform for Research Project
RISER	RISC-V for Cloud Services
SERRANO	TRANSPARENT APPLICATION DEPLOYMENT IN A SECURE, ACCELERATED AND COGNITIVE CLOUD CONTINUUM
SMARTEDGE	Semantic Low-code Programming Tools for Edge Intelligence
SODALITE	Software Defined Application Infrastructures management and Engineering
SovereignEdge.Cognit	A Cognitive Serverless Framework for the Cloud-Edge Continuum
SPADE	multi-purpoSe Physical-cyber Agri-forest Drones Ecosystem for governance and environmental observation
StandICT.eu 2026	ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
TaRDIS	A novel robotic parcel locker platform for cheap, efficient & convenient last-mile delivery
TEADAL	Trustworthy, Energy-Aware federated DAta Lakes along the computing continuum

TERMINET	nexT gEneRation sMart INterconnectEd IoT
TRUSTEE	TRUST AND PRIVACY PRESERVING COMPUTING PLATFORM FOR CROSS-BORDER FEDERATION OF DATA
UNICORE	A Common Code Base and Toolkit for Deployment of Applications to Secure and Reliable Virtual Execution Environments
VEDLIOT	Vsery Efficient Deep Learning n IoT
VeriDevOps	VeriDevOps
Vitamin-V	Virtual Environment and Tool-boxing for Trustworthy Development of RISC-V based Cloud Services
XANDAR	X-by-Construction Design framework for Engineering Autonomous & Distributed Real-time Embedded Software Systems

DRAFT